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● Three new species of the genus *Metipocregyes* Breuning, 1939 from Laos and Vietnam (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae: Lamiinae: Mesosini)

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Abstract: New species of the genus *Metipocregyes* Breuning, 1939 are described from continental Southeast Asia. *Metipocregyes pejchai* **sp. nov.**, *M. ryjaceki* **sp. nov.**, and *M. daklakensis* **sp. nov.** are described, illustrated and compared with similar species.

Keywords: Laos, longhorn beetles, Oriental Region, taxonomy, Vietnam

● 老挝与越南产深点天牛属三新种（鞘翅目：天牛科：沟胫天牛亚科：象天牛族）

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摘要: 本文描述了产自东南亚大陆的深点天牛属 *Metipocregyes* Breuning, 1939 的新种。文中对 *Metipocregyes pejchai* **sp. nov.**、*M. ryjaceki* **sp. nov.** 和 *M. daklakensis* **sp. nov.** 进行了描述、图示，并与近似种进行了比较。

关键词: 老挝，天牛，东洋区，分类学，越南

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● Introduction

The genus *Metipocregyes*, belonging to the tribe Mesosini, is widespread in Southeast Asia and South China. It was established by Breuning (1939) with the type species *Mesosa nodieri* Pic, 1933 from northern Vietnam. The genus contains eight known species, while significant part of them is known from Vietnam and Laos (Tavakilian & Chevillotte 2025). Authors who recently described new species of the genus *Metipocregyes* are Yamasako & Chou (2013), Yamasako & Lin (2018) and Gouverneur (2021). The most important contribution to the knowledge of the genus *Metipocregyes* is a review written by Yamasako & Lin (2018), which, in addition to the description of new species and new combinations, also contains an extended description of the genus *Metipocregyes*, redescriptions of previously known species of the genus and the key to the identification of species.

In this paper, three new species belonging to this genus are described and illustrated: *Metipocregyes pejchai* sp. nov. and *M. ryjaceki* sp. nov. from Laos, and *M. daklakensis* sp. nov. from Vietnam. The new species are compared with related species, some of them are hereby illustrated as well.

● Material and methods

Observation and photography. The habitus of specimens and genitalia photographs were taken using a Canon MP-E 65 mm f/2.8 1–5x Macro lens on bellows attached to a Canon EOS 550D camera. Each photograph was taken as several partially focused images, afterwards stacked in the Helicon Focus 8.2.18 Pro software. The photographs were modified using Adobe Photoshop CC.

Specimens examined including type materials are deposited in the following collections:

CMP Collection of Michal Pejcha, Ostrovačice, Czech Republic;

CPV Collection of Petr Viktora, Kutná Hora, Czech Republic.

A slash (/) separates data in different lines on locality and determination labels. Transcription of each label is followed by an abbreviation of collection in brackets.

● Taxonomy

Tribe Mesosini Latreille, 1802

Genus *Metipocregyes* Breuning, 1939

Type species. *Mesosa Nodieri* Pic, 1933.

Metipocregyes pejchai sp. nov.

<https://zoobank.org/C4949A71-FEAE-4D9E-9A88-A07473C914AE>

Figs 1–2

Type locality. Laos, Houaphanh Province, Xam Neua District, Phou Pan-Gnai Mountain [alternative names Phou Pan, Phou Pan-Gnai, Phou Pane], 20°12' N, 103°59' E.

Type material. Holotype (♂): 'NE LAOS, Hua Phan Prov., / MT. PHU PANE / 1200-1600m, 10.-22.V.2011 / 20,12N 103,59E / St. Jákł and Lao collectors lgt.', (CPV); Paratypes: (1 ♂, 7 ♀♀): same data as holotype, (CPV); (1 ♂, 1 ♀): 'NE LAOS: Houaphane prov. / Ban Saluei vill. env. / MT. PHU PANE, 1200-1900m / 26.4. - 10.5. 2013 / St. Jákł et local coll. lgt.', (CPV); (1 ♀): 'NE LAOS, May 2007, / Hua Phan Prov., / Mt. PHU PANE, / 1500-1900m, / Lao collector leg.', (CPV); (1 ♀): 'NE LAOS: Hua Phan prov. / Ban Saluei env. / MT. PHU PANE / 1200-1600m, 6.-20.5.2014 / P. Viktora et local coll. lgt.', (CPV); (2 ♀♀): 'Laos, Houa Phan, / 35 km S of Xam-Neua, / Ban Saleuey env. 1200-1700 m / 4.5.-17.5. 2006, M. Pejcha lgt.', (CMP).

The types are provided with a printed red label: 'Metipocregyes pejchai sp. nov. / HOLOTYPUS [respectively PARATYPUS] / P. Viktora det., 2026'.

Description. Habitus of male holotype as in Fig. 1a. Body from blackish brown to black, widely elongate, punctate, with pubescence and setation. Body length from head to elytral apex 12.95 mm (male paratypes from 10.60 to 12.00 mm), widest at humeral part of elytra (4.95 mm), 2.61 times as long as wide.

Head black, glossy, microwrinkled, with irregular, small-sized punctation, with narrow longitudinal furrow in middle. Head covered with dense, recumbent, creamy yellowish and blackish pubescence and long, erect, sparser, blackish setation. Head widest across eyes, narrower than pronotum at widest point. Eyes blackish brown, finely faceted, strongly emarginate (each eye separated into two parts, connected by a single row of sparsely spaced ommatidia). Upper part of eye significantly smaller than lower part. Space between antennal insertions wide, slightly depressed. Clypeus ochre yellow with blackish margins, shiny. Labrum blackish brown, finely wrinkled and punctured by dense micropunctation, covered with long, yellowish pubescence and long, erect, blackish setae in margins. Mandibles large, black, largely glossy, with long, yellowish pubescence and blackish setation at margins.

Maxillary palpus blackish, microwrinkled, partly with sparse, yellowish setation. Last palpomere longest, longitudinally grain-shaped, slightly narrowed apically with shortly yellowish tip.

Antennae with eleven antennomeres, black (antennal joint reddish brown), semi-glossy. Antennomeres microwrinkled, with dense, small-sized punctation. Antennomeres covered with creamy yellowish and blackish pubescence and long, erect, black (partly colourless) setation (mainly on inner side), as in Fig. 1a. Antennomeres 1–5 distinctly widened apically. Antennomeres without spines, rounded apically. Antennae extend beyond elytral apex by last five antennomeres (Fig. 1a). Scape long and robust, distinctly widened apically, shape of apical part as in Fig. 1a. Antennomere 3 distinctly longer than rest of antennomeres. Ratios of relative lengths of antennomeres 1–11 equal to: 0.76 : 0.19 : 1.00 : 0.74 : 0.54 : 0.43 : 0.37 : 0.33 : 0.30 : 0.30 : 0.32.

Pronotum black, transverse, narrower than elytra, narrowest at anterior margin, 1.40 times as wide as long at widest point (two fifths of pronotal length from base to anterior margin). Pronotum glossy, with strangulation at anterior third, with strongly corrugated surface (with large humps, partly with large irregular punctures), microwrinkled, partly with shallow, small-sized, dense punctation, partly covered with recumbent creamy yellowish pubescence and sparser, dark pubescence in dark areas. Pronotal disc with long, erect, dark setation. Lateral margins undulate, base slightly undulate, anterior margin arcuate (shape of pronotum as in Fig. 1a). Pronotal disc relatively flat.

Scutellum small, black, with dense micropunctation, covered with long, recumbent, creamy yellowish pubescence in middle.

Elytra 8.95 mm long and 4.95 mm wide (1.80 times as long as wide), slightly narrowing apically (strongly narrowed at apical quarter), black, glossy, with strongly corrugated surface (with large humps, partly with large irregular punctures mainly at basal half), with dense micropunctation, with distinct humps near scutellum and at humeri. Elytra covered with recumbent, creamy yellowish pubescence and sparser, dark pubescence in dark areas, elytral disc with very long, erect, dark setae at basal third. Elytral disc only slightly rounded (almost flat at basal part). Elytra widest at humeri. Elytral apical margin broadly rounded, without spines, sutural angles angularly rounded.

Legs largely black, semi-glossy, with dense micropunctation. Legs (including tarsi and claws) covered with dense, creamy yellowish and sparser, darker pubescence (in dark areas) and relatively dense, very long, erect setation of several shades. Tibiae distinctly widened apically. Metatarsomeres 2 and 3 combined 1.90 times longer than metatarsomere 1.

Ventral side of body black, with dense small-sized punctation/micropunctation, largely covered with dense, recumbent, creamy yellowish pubescence, partly with a few small, dark spots, almost completely covered with long, erect, colourless setation. Elytral epipleura black, narrow, covered with pubescence of the same colour and intensity as in elytra.

FIGURE 1. *Metipocregyes pejchai* sp. nov.: a male holotype b male genitalia.

FIGURE 2. *Metipocregyes pejchai* sp. nov.: female paratype.

FIGURE 3. *Metipocregyes affinis* Breuning, 1968: female from Thailand, Chiang Rai Province, (CPV).

Genitalia as in Fig. 1b.

Female. Habitus of female paratype as in Fig. 2. Body length from head to elytral apex (female paratypes) from 11.40 to 15.90 mm. Colour of female similar to male. Female more robust, with less elongate elytra, antennae shorter than in male, not reaching elytral apex (Figs. 1a and 2).

Variability. A species with a relatively large size variance (see above). Intensity and size of the spots of pale and dark pubescence on elytra individually highly variable, but always within similar pattern.

Differential diagnosis. The most similar species are *Metipocregyes nodieri* (Pic, 1933) (Fig. 7) and *M. affinis* Breuning, 1968 (Fig. 3).

Metipocregyes pejchai **sp. nov.** differs from the similar species *M. nodieri* by wider pronotum, different colouration of pubescence in pronotum, elytra, legs and antennae (dominating unicoloured creamy yellowish in *M. pejchai*, while creating a marbling of mostly greyish shade with creamy yellowish small spots near basal margin and large yellowish spot at apical third of elytra in *M. nodieri*). *M. pejchai* has ventral side of body covered with creamy yellowish pubescence, partly with a few small, dark spots, while *M. nodieri* has ventral side largely greyish with pronounced dark marbling (prominent marbling also on ventral side of femora in *M. nodieri*). *M. pejchai* has distinctly sparser punctation of elytra (Figs. 2 and 7).

Metipocregyes pejchai **sp. nov.** (based on comparison of females) differs from the similar species *M. affinis* by legs and antennae black (distinctly reddish brown in *M. affinis*), wider pronotum of different shape (more transverse), different shades of pale pubescence on pronotum and elytra (dominating unicoloured creamy yellowish in *M. pejchai*, while creating a marbling of greyish shades (even though setae are in fact whitish) with creamy yellowish small spots mainly near basal margin and at apical third of elytra in *M. affinis*). Pattern of pale pubescent spots on elytra very stable in *M. affinis* (based on type specimen and additional specimens from northern Thailand), while very variable in *M. pejchai*. *M. pejchai* has ventral side of body covered with creamy yellowish pubescence, partly with a few small, dark spots, while *M. affinis* has ventral side visually greyish with pronounced dark marbling. *M. pejchai* has antennae with much larger proportion of pale pubescence and adequately lower proportion of dark areas than in *M. affinis*, while this character is most prominent on scape and antennomeres 3–4 (Figs. 2–3).

Note. Yamasako & Lin (2018) report records of the species *Metipocregyes affinis* Breuning, 1968 from Mt. Phou Pan-Gnai in Houaphanh province of Laos and Mt. Samsoum in Xieng Khouang province of Laos. Unfortunately, illustrated specimens, designated as *M. affinis* (Yamasako & Lin 2018: 506, figs. 5–8) are misidentified and belong to the species *Metipocregyes pejchai* **sp. nov.** described above. For differences between both species see differential diagnosis above. I personally had the opportunity to visit both of the mentioned localities several times and I studied an extensive material of the tribe Mesosini from the locality of Mt. Phou Pan-Gnai, collected over many years by me and my Czech colleagues. I can safely say that I have not come across a specimen from this locality that would match all morphological characters of the species *M. affinis*. The identification of specimens from Laos, reported in Yamasako & Lin (2018), therefore needs to be verified and eventually corrected with impact to faunal data for the species *M. affinis* in Laos.

Etymology. The species is dedicated to Michal Pejcha (Ostrovačice, Czech Republic), my friend and one of the collectors of this new species.

Distribution. Laos (Houaphanh).

Metipocregyes affinis Breuning, 1968

Fig. 3

Additional material. (1 ♀): ‘N THAILAND / Chiang Rai prov. / Wiang Pa Pao env. / 7. - 22. V. 2010 / P. Viktora lgt.’, (CPV); (1 ♀): ‘N THAILAND / Chiang Rai prov. / Wiang Pa Pao env. / 21. 5. - 10. 6. 2011 / P. Viktora lgt.’, (CPV).

New province record.

Distribution. Laos (Vientiane, Xieng Khouang, Houaphanh), Thailand (Chiang Mai, Chiang Rai).

Note. Based on the incorrect identification of illustrated specimens in Yamasako & Lin (2018), an identification of specimens from Lao provinces Xieng Khouang and Houaphanh, mentioned in their work, needs to be verified and eventually corrected.

***Metipocregyes ryjaceki* sp. nov.**

<https://zoobank.org/CAA5E04C-646F-45E5-A00A-439A2720346A>

Figs 4–5

Type locality. Laos, Attapeu Province, Annam Highlands Mountains, Dong Ampham National Biodiversity Conservation Area, Nong Fa Lake [alternative name Nongphatom Lake] environs, 15°05.9' N, 107°25.6' E.

Type material. Holotype (♂): 'LAOS, ATTAPEU prov. / Annam Highlands Mts. / Dong Ampham NBCA, ca. 1160 m / NONG FA [crater lake] env. / 15°05.9'N, 107°25.6'E / Vít Ryjáček leg. 30.IV-6.V.2010', (CPV); Paratype: (1 ♀): 'LAOS: Attapeu prov., / Annam Highlands Mts. / cca 1150m, NONG FA / (crater lake env.) / 30.4.-4.5.2010, St. Jakl lgt.', (CPV). The types are provided with a printed red label: 'Metipocregyes ryjaceki sp. nov. / HOLOTYPUS [respectively PARATYPUS] / P. Viktora det., 2026'.

Description. Habitus of male holotype as in Fig. 4a. Body from pale reddish brown to black, largely glossy, widely elongate, punctate, with pubescence and setation. Body length from head to elytral apex 9.85 mm, widest at humeral part of elytra (4.00 mm), 2.46 times as long as wide.

Head largely black (antennal insertions and margins dark brown), semi-glossy, with dense, small-sized punctation/micropunctation, with narrow longitudinal furrow in middle. Head covered with recumbent, pale, ochre yellowish pubescence and long, erect, sparser, ochre setation. Head widest across eyes, distinctly narrower than pronotum at widest point. Eyes goldenish brown, finely faceted, strongly emarginate (each eye separated into two parts, connected by four rows of ommatidia). Upper part of eye significantly smaller than lower part. Space between antennal insertions wide, flat. Clypeus and labrum pale ochre yellow, shiny, covered with long, yellowish pubescence and setation at margins. Mandibles large, from brown to black tip, semi-glossy, with long, yellowish pubescence and setation at margins.

Maxillary palpus blackish brown, microwrinkled, partly with indistinct, sparse, shiny setation. Last palpomere longest, longitudinally grain-shaped, distinctly narrowed apically with shortly pale reddish brown tip.

Antennae with eleven antennomeres, semi-glossy, from pale reddish brown to dark reddish brown in last antennomeres. Antennomeres microwrinkled, with dense, small-sized punctation. Antennomeres covered with pale, ochre yellowish and darker pubescence and long, erect, dark (partly colourless) setation (mainly on antennomeres 1–4), antennomere 4 with distinct, dense tuft of black setae at apical half (Fig. 4a). Antennomeres 1–5 distinctly widened apically. Antennomeres without spines, rounded apically. Antennae slightly extended beyond elytral apex (Fig. 4a). Scape long and distinct, widened apically, shape of apical part as in Fig. 4a. Antennomere 3 distinctly longer than rest of antennomeres. Ratios of relative lengths of antennomeres 1–11 equal to: 0.80 : 0.16 : 1.00 : 0.64 : 0.35 : 0.28 : 0.24 : 0.22 : 0.20 : 0.19 : 0.21.

Pronotum largely dark reddish brown, transverse, distinctly narrower than elytra, narrowest at anterior margin, 1.36 times as wide as long at widest point (near middle of pronotum). Pronotum glossy, with smooth depression of inverted triangle shape at anterior part of pronotal disc, with corrugated surface (with humps, partly with large irregular punctures), microwrinkled, partly with shallow, small-sized, dense punctation/micropunctation, partly covered with recumbent pale, ochre yellowish pubescence and sparser, ochre pubescence with lustre in dark areas. Pronotal disc with long, erect, dark setation of several shades. Lateral margins undulate, base slightly undulate, anterior margin arcuate (shape of pronotum as in Fig. 4a). Pronotal disc relatively flat.

FIGURE 4. *Metipocregyes ryjaceki* sp. nov.: **a** male holotype **b** male genitalia.

Scutellum small, black, with dense micropunctuation, covered with long, recumbent, yellowish pubescence in middle.

Elytra 6.65 mm long and 4.00 mm wide (1.66 times as long as wide), narrowing apically, dark reddish brown, glossy, with corrugated surface (with humps, partly with large irregular punctures mainly at basal half), with dense micropunctuation, with tubercles nearby scutellum and at humeri. Elytra covered with recumbent, pale, ochre yellowish pubescence and darker, ochre pubescence with lustre. Elytral disc only slightly rounded, partly with very long, erect, dark setae. Elytra widest at humeri. Elytral apical margin broadly rounded, without spines, sutural angles angularly rounded.

Legs from reddish brown to blackish brown, semi-glossy, with dense micropunctuation. Legs (including tarsi) covered with long, pale, ochre yellowish pubescence, and very long, erect, pale setation. Tibiae widened apically. Metatarsomeres 2 and 3 combined 1.30 times longer than metatarsomere 1.

Ventral side of body from pale reddish brown to blackish brown (largely brown), with dense small-sized punctuation/micropunctuation, almost completely covered with dense, recumbent, pale, ochre yellowish pubescence and with very long, erect, colourless setation. Elytral epipleura brown, narrow, covered with pubescence and setation of the same colour and intensity as in elytra.

Genitalia as in Fig. 4b.

Female. Habitus of female paratype as in Fig. 5. Body length from head to elytral apex 13.50 mm. Colour of female similar to male. Female more robust, pronotum wider and more transverse (pronotal disc with three transverse carinae in middle of basal half), elytra with a few larger and more visible spots of pale pubescence (mainly at apical half), antennae shorter than in male, not reaching elytral apex (Figs. 4a and 5).

Differential diagnosis. The most similar species is *Metipocregyes affinis* Breuning, 1968 (Fig. 3).

Metipocregyes ryjaceki **sp. nov.** (based on comparison of females) differs from the similar species *M. affinis* by wider pronotum of different shape (more transverse with three carinae on pronotal disc), different shades of pale pubescence on elytra (dominating ochre yellowish of several shades in *M. ryjaceki*, while creating a marbling of greyish shades (even though setae are in fact whitish) with creamy yellowish small spots mainly near basal margin and at apical third of elytra in *M. affinis*). Distinctive character is different colour and distribution of pale and dark pubescence in antennae, *M. ryjaceki* has antennomere 4 with distinct, dense tuft of black setae at apical half, which is missing in *M. affinis* (Figs. 3 and 5).

Etymology. The species is dedicated to Vít Ryjáček (Dobřichovice, Czech Republic), my friend and one of the collectors of this new species.

Distribution. Laos (Attapeu).

Metipocregyes daklakensis **sp. nov.**

<https://zoobank.org/62E01C82-8E3E-4B7C-9680-6A6A2DFD393A>

Fig. 6

Type locality. Vietnam, Dak Lak Province.

Type material. Holotype (♀): ‘Vietnam / Dak Lak / 5/2025 / local collector leg.’, (CPV).

The type is provided with a printed red label: ‘*Metipocregyes daklakensis* sp. nov. / HOLOTYPUS / P. Viktora det., 2026’.

Description. Habitus of female holotype as in Fig. 6. Body from blackish brown to black, robust, widely elongate, punctate, with pubescence and setation. Body length from head to elytral apex 15.60 mm, widest at elytral humeral part (6.55 mm), 2.38 times as long as wide.

Head black, semi-glossy, microwrinkled, with irregular, dense, small-sized punctation/granulation, with distinct, almost smooth, narrow longitudinal furrow in middle. Head covered with dense, long, recumbent, ochre pubescence and sparser, shorter blackish pubescence. Head partly with sparse, long, erect setation of several shades. Head narrower than pronotum at widest point. Eyes blackish, finely faceted, strongly emarginate (each eye separated into two parts, connected by two rows of sparsely spaced ommatidia). Upper part of eye significantly smaller than lower part. Space between antennal insertions wide, slightly depressed. Clypeus and labrum pale ochre yellow, shiny, covered with long, yellowish pubescence and darker setation at margins. Mandibles large, black, glossy, with long, yellowish pubescence and dark setation at margins.

Maxillary palpus black (palpomeres with narrowly paler, reddish brown apex), with shallow, dense, small-sized punctation, partly with sparse, indistinct yellowish pubescence and distinct, erect yellowish setation (shorter and denser setation with a few very long, erect setae). Last palpomere longest, longitudinally grain-shaped, distinctly narrowed apically, with pale reddish brown, tip cut.

Antennae with eleven antennomeres, antennomeres reddish brown, partly with narrowly darker apex, semi-glossy. Antennomeres with dense, shallow, small-sized punctation (scape with a few large, shallow punctures). Scape covered with sparse, long ochre pubescence of several shades, antennomeres 2–11 covered with pale yellowish/whitish pubescence and darker pubescence at apical parts. Antennomeres 1–3 with long, erect setae on inner as well as outer side, antennomere 4 with long, erect setae of several shades on inner side, and with distinct, dense tuft of black setae at apical three fifths (Fig. 6), antennomeres 5–10 with a few long, erect setae at apical parts. Antennomeres 1–10 widened apically. Antennomeres without spines, antennomeres 2–3 rounded apically. Antennae reaching five sixths of elytral length (Fig. 6). Scape longest, distinct, widened apically, shape of apical part as in Fig. 6. Ratios of relative lengths of antennomeres 1–11 equal to: 1.05 : 0.18 : 1.00 : 0.72 : 0.37 : 0.26 : 0.20 : 0.18 : 0.17 : 0.18 : 0.19.

Pronotum black, transverse, distinctly narrower than elytra, narrowest at anterior margin, 1.52 times as wide as long at widest point (approximately at two fifths of pronotal length from base to anterior margin). Pronotum semi-glossy, with smooth depression of inverted triangle shape at anterior part of pronotal disc, with strongly corrugated surface (with large humps, partly with large irregular tubercles), microwrinkled, partly with shallow, small-sized, dense punctation, partly covered with recumbent ochre pubescence and sparser, dark pubescence in dark areas. Pronotal disc with long, erect, dark setation. Lateral margins undulate, base slightly undulate, anterior margin slightly arcuate and undulate (shape of pronotum as in Fig. 6). Pronotal disc relatively flat, slightly undulate.

Scutellum small, black, with dense micropunctation, partly covered with spots of recumbent, ochre pubescence.

Elytra 10.55 mm long and 6.55 mm wide (1.61 times as long as wide), slightly narrowing apically, black, glossy, with strongly corrugated surface (with large humps, partly with large irregular tubercles), microwrinkled, with distinct humps nearby scutellum and at humeri. Elytra covered with recumbent, ochre pubescence of several shades and sparser, black pubescence in dark areas, elytral disc with very long, erect setae of several shades. Elytral disc only slightly rounded. Elytra widest at humeri. Elytral apical margin broadly rounded, without spines, sutural angles angularly rounded.

Legs largely reddish brown (femora blackish apically), semi-glossy, with dense, shallow, small-sized punctation. Tarsi dark brown, claws reddish brown. Legs (including tarsi and claws) covered with long, ochre pubescence of several shades and very long, dense, erect setae (pale yellowish in paler areas, blackish at apical parts of tibiae). Tibiae distinctly widened apically. Tarsi short, wide. Metatarsomeres 2 and 3 combined 2.04 times longer than metatarsomere 1.

Ventral side of body from brown to black (largely black), with small-sized, irregular granulation/punctation, largely covered with dense, recumbent, ochre pubescence of several shades, partly with small, dark spots, almost completely covered with long, erect, colourless setation. Elytral epipleura blackish, narrow, covered with pubescence of the same colour and intensity as in elytra.

Male. Unknown.

Differential diagnosis. The most similar species is *Metipocregyes fruhstorferi* (Breuning, 1959) (Fig. 8).

Metipocregyes daklakensis **sp. nov.** (based on comparison of females) differs from the similar species *M. fruhstorferi* by legs largely reddish brown (legs largely black in *M. fruhstorferi*), longer antennae, wider pronotum of different shape (more transverse), different shades of pale pubescence in elytra (several shades of ochre in *M. daklakensis*, while several shades of ochre and partly creating a marbling of greyish shades (even though setae are in fact whitish) mainly at the basal third and preapical part of elytra in *M. fruhstorferi*), larger humps of different shape near scutellum and at humeri, pronotal disc with denser and more distinct tuberculation, and by different colour and density of pubescence in femora (Figs. 6 and 8).

Etymology. Named after the type locality, Dak Lak Province.

Distribution. Vietnam (Dak Lak).

Metipocregyes nodieri (Pic, 1933)

Fig. 7

Additional material. (3 ♂♂, 1 ♀): ‘Vietnam / Yen Bai / 5/2023’, (CPV); (1 ♂): ‘Mt. Jianfengling. Main peak, Jianfeng Township, / Ledong Li Autonomous County, Hainan, China / 11-VI-2017 / 1412m / 18°43′0.85″ N, / 108°52′17.74″ E, 107°25.6′ E / coll. Shiliang MO, (CPV).

Distribution. Vietnam (Ha Giang [it was merged with Tuyen Quang province in 2025], Vinh Phuc [it was dissolved and merged with Phu Tho province in 2025], Yen Bai [it was dissolved and merged with Lao Cai province in 2025]), China (Guangxi, Hainan, Yunnan).

FIGURE 5. *Metipocregyes ryjaceki* sp. nov.: female paratype.

FIGURE 6. *Metipocregyes daklakensis* sp. nov.: female holotype.

FIGURE 7. *Metipocregyes nodieri* (Pic, 1933): male from Vietnam, Yen Bai Province, (CPV).

FIGURE 8. *Metipocregyes fruhstorferi* (Breuning, 1959): female from Laos, Houaphanh Province, (CPV).

Metipocregyes fruhstorferi (Breuning, 1959)

Fig. 8

Additional material. (1 ♀): ‘LAOS-NE, Houa Phan pr. / Ban Saluei v. - Mt. Phou Pane / 1920-1450m, 10.-21.VI.2010 / St. Jakl et local collectors lgt.’, (CPV); (1 ♀): ‘NE LAOS, / Hua Phan Prov., MT. PHU PANE, / 900 - 16000 m, 10-21.06.2010 / 20° 12’ N 103° 59’ E / St. Jakl and Lao collectors lgt.’, (CPV).

Distribution. Vietnam (Lang Son, Vinh Phuc [it was dissolved and merged with Phu Tho province in 2025]), Laos (Houaphanh).

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Photo Gallery

广西华缺翅螳 *Sinomiopteryx guangxiensis* Wang & Bi, 1993
Shengtangshan Scenic Area [圣堂山景区], Dayao Mountains, Guangxi
photograph by Zi-Hao ZHU [朱梓豪]